

SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF SPEECH DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS WITH MENTAL DISABILITY BASED ON FAIRY TALE THERAPY

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Abstract: In this article, there are opinions about the specific features of speech development of mentally retarded students based on fairy tale therapy.

Key words: Educational system, mentally retarded student, methodology, speech skills, fairy tale.

INTRODUCTION.

In the years of independence, the field of education became one of the priority directions of our state policy. An example of this is the scale and weight of the work being done in this regard. The high attention of our government to this field is reflected in the achievements and large-scale changes in the development of education in a short period of time. On the basis of the government's decisions aimed at reforming and developing education, education of a mature generation is considered as the main task. This thing, in turn, is an important part of education of the national idea.

One of the most important qualities of a person is his ability to speak, the ability to communicate and think through speech. Meaningful speech is the result of the activity of certain organisms, which is the result of the combination of different sounds in a certain order. Speech is a complex functional process. It is based on the appropriate use of language units in the communication process. The complex system of the language is a product of long-term socio-historical development and is acquired by the child in a relatively short period of time. In the process of speech development, higher forms of cognitive activity and thinking abilities are formed.

The meaning of the word is self-generalizing, and in this regard, it shows not only the unity of speech, but also the unity of thought. They are not exactly the same and to some extent appear independently of each other. But in the process of the child's mental development, a new unity of speech thinking and speech thinking activity appears in terms of its complex quality. The process of interaction between people through language is called speech. Speech and language should not be considered the same thing. Speech is an activity in which a person uses language to communicate with other people. Each moment makes the transaction in its own way. But this transaction takes place with the same means used by a particular nation.

According to the method of expression, the speech is oral and written. Oral speech differs from written speech in the following ways: oral speech is sound speech, and written speech is graphic speech. In oral speech, the auditory sense plays a major role, using intonation, facial expressions, and gesticulation. In written speech, sight and motor sense play the main role. Helps to understand written speech more clearly. Oral speech and written speech serve as a means of communication between people. Oral speech can be monologic

and diological speech. As the name suggests, a monologue is a speech by one person. It is often directed at other people to the audience (report, story), but monologic speech should be understandable to the audience while it is being addressed.

Along with mental processes, the ability to hear is very important in the development of a child. In the normal development of this and in general, the ability to hear is closely related to all mental processes, and only when it develops without any defects, the child's speech will develop at a normal level. The characteristic of a mentally retarded child is that his psyche is formed in the process of anomalous development in conditions that do not obey the rules. A mentally retarded child differs from his healthy peers in that his previous experience and development have not formed the mechanisms and mental processes necessary for further mental development. Thus, the general level of mental development of a mentally retarded child cannot ensure that he acquires school knowledge, skills and abilities in a conscious manner under normal conditions.

The child's mental development is not sufficiently prepared, he cannot focus on the purpose of the educational tasks, he cannot overcome difficulties. The order in the school does not obey the rules. All this leads to lack of mastery. Therefore, one of the important tasks of the auxiliary school is to introduce corrective moments into the pedagogical process in order to advance the student in his general development. Leading activity not only requires the most basic changes in his mental processes and personal characteristics, but is also a good indicator of his growth. B. N. Pinsky stated that children with mental retardation need propaedeutic and corrective educational activities so that they can perform tasks that their healthy peers can perform independently or with a little help from the teacher. Proper acquisition of speech at the right time allows the child to communicate freely with the people around him, helps him control his speech, and finally makes the process of education at school much easier.

Mentally retarded children learn language much later than their healthy peers. The term of the first word is delayed until the child is three, sometimes five years old. First of all, it is necessary to note here the defects in pronunciation. According to G.A. Cain's research, 66% of secondary school students experience some form of stuttering. It is not a coincidence that such a large number of speech defects occur in mentally retarded children. Already damage to the cortex of the brain leads to a violation of phonemic hearing and a loss of movement of the articulatory apparatus. Mentally retarded children face serious difficulties in acquiring the vocabulary of the language. The reserve of words used by students with mental retardation is so narrow that it cannot be compared to the normal standard. They often do not understand the meaning of words.

In the speech of secondary school students, compound sentences are usually found in the elementary form in simple conjunctions. Because students find it difficult to reveal the causal connections of events when comparing one thing to another. This kind of liveliness in the structure of sentences corresponds to simple connections formed in the cerebral cortex of a mentally retarded child. In addition, the lack of clear understanding of the connections leads to the incompleteness of the thinking of mentally retarded students. Children make a number of mistakes about what they read, hear, and see. Mentally retarded children, even 1st graders, cannot always follow the verbal instructions of others. The experiments conducted by A.R. Luria, N.P. Paramanova, O.K. Tikhomirov and others show that a mentally retarded child is not able to independently express the general rules that can serve as a guide for his actions. The

internal speech of a mentally retarded child is more damaged than the external speech. Inner speech is the material shell of any thought formed in the mind. Such defects in the speech of mentally retarded children make it difficult for them to read. Pupils do not always understand the teacher's explanations, they do not understand the content of the text independently, they weakly control their actions with the learned rule. For them, the word is confused with the thing itself, and it takes a lot of courage to separate it from its concrete meaning, that is, to start studying it from a grammatical and phonetic point of view.

Such children do not pay attention to the graphic representation of words. Only careful letter-by-letter analysis will help them draw the right conclusions. Here, it is not correct to consider the characteristics of mentally retarded children as absolutely insurmountable and immutable. The experiences of advanced pedagogues - defectologists show that with the help of a specially organized system of education, it is possible to correct the defects in the speech activity of the mentally retarded, and to increase the defects in the delay in thinking.

Mentally retarded children distort many sounds, i.e. sliding back of the tongue, sonorous sounds. Such a situation indicates that the child's speech apparatus is not well developed. Children belonging to this group have a higher percentage of distorting sounds and replacing them with other sounds. That is why the main task of speech therapists and teachers is to develop the speech of mentally retarded children in every way. Correct pronunciation of sounds depends on the child's articulatory apparatus working well. That is why the main task of speech therapists and teachers is to develop the speech of mentally retarded children in every way. The correct pronunciation of sounds depends on the child's articulatory apparatus being well coordinated and adapted. That's why articulatory exercises are always carried out while working on sounds. Some vowels and consonants are acquired slowly. Most of the children have difficulty pronouncing certain sounds, i.e. R, S, K, G, M, Sh, Ch, and pronounce words incorrectly.

General motor underdevelopment, which is typical for mentally retarded children, also plays a certain role in slowing down the development of speech. Failure to develop motor skills (movements) disrupts the process of the child's acquaintance with the world around them and, as a result, inhibits the collection of ideas and information about them. Defects in motor skills observed in mentally retarded children also affect the pronunciation side of their speech. Because the voluntary pronunciation of speech sounds requires high-level coordination efforts of speech organs. For mentally retarded children, coordinated movements of speech organs are difficult. Poor development of phonetic hearing and speech movement deficits, which are characteristic of children with mental retardation, affect each other and inhibit the development of speech. However, it should be noted that it would not be appropriate to exaggerate the shortcomings of the speech organs, because these disorders can be easily eliminated later. The main leading role belongs to the underdevelopment of phonemic hearing, which is a consequence of defects in the general development of mentally retarded children.

Connected speech is not formed in mentally retarded children of preschool age. They cannot participate in the dialogue. Monologue speech causes great difficulties for mentally retarded children. Mentally retarded children of senior preschool age and elementary school students cannot switch to independent extensive expression through speech for a long time. They always need the help of adults to express their thoughts verbally. In normally developing children, the formation of the phonemic aspect of speech takes place at the age of

4-5 years. In the process of acquiring the mother tongue, he learns to distinguish words from the flow of speech, to analyze them, to hear and pronounce their main meaningful phonemes - sounds. Gradually, as the work of the organs of articulation improves and the semantic aspect of speech is mastered, the child's pronunciation becomes more correct and his language conforms to the phonetic norms by the time he goes to school.

Defects in the pronunciation of mentally retarded children are one of the manifestations of the incomplete development of speech. Unlike the pronunciation defects observed in normally developing children, the pronunciation defects found in mentally retarded children have other, more complex, and therefore difficult to eliminate causes. They are based on the slowing down of the child's mastery of the sound side of the mother tongue. A mentally retarded child is characterized by phonetic-phonemic disorders, manifested by difficulties in distinguishing phonemes that are similar in sound and analyzing the sound of words. These cause pronunciation defects. Without being able to distinguish sounds that are similar in reality, the child will not be able to learn to pronounce them correctly, because he will not be able to improve his own pronunciation control.

Defects in sound analysis and synthesis of the word, in turn, prevent us from mastering their structure. Omission of sounds in words leads to substitution, as well as not saying the end of the word. In mentally retarded children, poor phonemic hearing and various pronunciation defects do not affect children's writing and reading activities. Mentally retarded children write letters of similar shape interchangeably. Among them there are also children whose analyzers are broken. Deficiencies in this content are eliminated by individual corrective actions.

In mentally retarded children, phonemic defects of speech are manifested in different ways. In some children, they are clearly manifested. Children do not pronounce some sounds at all (Sh, R, K, etc.), they pronounce a number of sounds vaguely (L, Z, B), sounds that are similar in terms of articulation and hearing are replaced. Some children with mental retardation have speech stuttering, which may be accompanied by speech disorders or other speech disorders. Undoubtedly, pronunciation defects are more common in mentally retarded children than in normally developing children. According to G.A. Kashe, 65% of the students of the 1st grade and 60% of the 2nd grade students of the auxiliary school have pronunciation defects of one or another level. According to I.P. Kornev's observations, 60% of mentally retarded children have various pronunciation difficulties when they are admitted to an auxiliary school. Even after the elimination of defects in the pronunciation of sounds, mentally retarded children can pronounce sounds separately, but they cannot use these sounds in independent speech. Because the use of sounds in one's active speech is a really complex activity compared to the pronunciation of individual sounds.

When communicating with mentally retarded children, it is noticeable that their speech is not expressive enough. Accent separation and intonation of the sentence serve as the main means of phonetic expressiveness of oral speech. The means of expression in oral speech of mentally retarded children are very weak. Their speech is characterized by monotony, unnecessary pauses without intonation.

In some cases, there is a pathologic slow-down or accelerated excitation. It is observed that the vocabulary of children with mental retardation is usually very slow. They often don't even know the names of well-known objects. According to G.L. Vigotsky, nouns and verbs

dominate the vocabulary of 1st-2nd grade students with mental retardation. G. M. Dulnev shows that mentally retarded children rarely use adjectives in their speech.

Children with mental retardation often understand and use words inappropriately and in a broad sense when naming the qualities of objects. For example, the word "big" means not only the size of an object, but also its weight, length, thickness, height, and dimensions. At the basis of these characteristics, the processes of mentally retarded children, in particular, are unique in analysis and synthesis. Children with mental retardation, unable to perceive clearly enough of those around them, dedifferentiate and limit themselves to generalized abstract names.

It is observed that the inactive vocabulary of mentally retarded children is superior to the active vocabulary. (G.M. Dulnev) in mentally retarded children, most of the words are included in their inactive vocabulary, and very few of them are used in speech. One of the main factors inhibiting the speech development of children with mental retardation is the lack of mastering the semantic side of the native language, which is characteristic of children of this category. It is known that children pronounce and distinguish familiar words much easier. So, the meaning of the word plays an important role in directing and organizing the child's phonemic hearing. General developmental disabilities prevent children with mental retardation from understanding the words spoken by others while naming objects or performing actions. Defects in understanding the meaning of words, in turn, complicate the development of phonemic hearing, thereby inhibiting the formation of a child's speech.

In a normally developing preschool child, speech is formed in close connection with the direct realization of life experience and communication with others. Active practical and educational activity of the child expands the scope of his imagination, stimulates the emergence of new needs and interests. This, in turn, leads to a sharp increase in the child's need for speech communication with adults. By communicating with adults, the child enriches his vocabulary, learns new meanings of words, learns vocabulary, and then uses them to express his desires, feelings, attitude to other people, and expressions. The development of speech even in young children with mental retardation is definitely related to increasing their life experience and communication with others. But the general underdevelopment of the psyche means that their expansion of experience is slow and defective. Improperly developing practical and cognitive activity cannot be a sufficient basis for the rapid collection of a large number of different ideas.

A mentally retarded child feels needs in moderation and does not communicate enough. Communication with adults is formed in mentally retarded children with late and deviations from the norm. In hydrocephalus, which causes mental retardation, sometimes it seems that speech is well developed, but in reality it is not so. In the speech of such children, there are very complex sentences and words, they are distinguished by the fact that the grammatical structure of the speech is also very complicated. The thinking of these children seems instructive. They do not understand the essence of the speech. Even if children's speech is well developed, it cannot be a thinking tool for mentally retarded children. Such peculiar speech in dementia is rare. The speech of mentally retarded children with schizophrenia is similar to the above. These children can develop speech skills faster than healthy children. Their wealth is little different from that of normal children. But they may encounter broken words in their speech. There are no significant changes in the oral speech of children with brain injuries, rheumatism, and mental retardation, while there are sufficient deficiencies in

their written speech. Writing skills of such children are formed very slowly. At first glance, the speech of children suffering from epilepsy is similar to the speech of children with mental retardation, these children tend to repeat the same sentences and words. There are too many hiccups in their speech.

As we mentioned above, 40-60% of secondary school students have various speech defects. Among these defects, the main part is dry tongue, stuttering, and stuttering. The role of the speech of mentally retarded children as a means of communication is damaged from all sides. In this case, the functions of information, emotional-will, control of speech are violated. In such children, there is no correspondence between speech and activity. Inconsistency is noticeable between the speech of a mentally retarded child and his behavior. Mentally retarded children cannot use their speech to control themselves. A.R. Luria said that healthy children can use speech as a tool of control even at the age of kindergarten.

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